

SHORT NOTES

Dissociation Constant of 5-Nitro-1,10-phenanthroline

S. C. Lahiri and S. Aditya

Dissociation constant of 5-nitro-1,10-phenanthroline in water has been determined at different temperatures by spectrophotometric method. Brandt and Gullstrom¹ determined the dissociation constant at 25° by pH-titration in water-dioxane mixture.

5-Nitro-1,10-phenanthroline hydrochloride was prepared by dissolving the substance (B. D. H.) in excess hydrochloric acid. It absorbs in the UV region. Other chemicals used were of reagent grade. The solutions were prepared in double distilled water.

Procedure—The absorption spectra of 5-nitro-1,10-phenanthrolium ion and that of the neutral molecule were obtained by preparing solutions containing *N*/5 HCl and neutral as well as alkaline solutions (pH 7-10). The phenanthrolium ion showed maximum absorption at 276 m μ and the neutral molecule at 268 m μ .

To determine the dissociation constant of the base, optical densities of 5-nitro-1,10-phenanthroline ($\approx 10^{-5}M$) in different sodium acetate-HCl buffers of constant ionic strength 0.2 (pH 2.64-4.19; Walpole²) in *N*/5-HCl and in neutral solutions were measured at 280 m μ (chosen as the difference in absorption by the ionic and the molecular form is maximum at this wave length) and at 25°, 30°, 35°, and 45°. The blank solutions were of the same composition as in the experimental solutions excepting 5-nitro-1,10-phenanthroline. All measurements of optical density were taken in duplicate with a Beckman DU quartz spectrophotometer, fitted with a thermostated cell-holder.

The thermodynamic dissociation constant K_T for $BH^+ \rightleftharpoons B + H^+$ (where B=5-nitro-1,10-phenanthroline) is given by

$$pK_T = pH + \log \frac{d - d_M}{d_I - d} + \log f_{BH^+}$$

where d =O.D. of the mixture of ion and molecule at the analytical wave length and d_M and d_I represent respectively the O.D. of the molecule and the ion at the same wave length.

The pHs of the buffers are known. The optical densities d_M , d_I , and d at any suitable wave length will provide pK_T , in the calculation of which Davies equation³ for activity coefficient has been used.

1. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 3532.

2. Britton, "Hydrogen Ions", Vol. I, D. Van Nostrand Company Inc., p. 353.

3. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 2093.

The difference between our value (3.23) and Brandt and Gullstrom's (3.57) at 25° is probably due to the fact that these authors used a mixed solvent (dioxane-water) and used an extrapolation to get equilibrium constant in water. Further, it is not clear if their value is for the thermodynamic constant. The results are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Temp.	No. of readings.	pK_T .
25°	8	3.230(±0.01)
30°	7	3.210(±0.01)
35°	7	3.175(±0.015)
45°	7	3.120(±0.011)

From the values of the constant at 25°, 30°, 35°, and 45°, ΔH and ΔS have been calculated.

$$\Delta F \text{ at } 25^\circ = 4.406 \text{ kcal./mole.}$$

$$\Delta H = 2.26 (\pm 0.1) \text{ kcal./mole.}$$

$$\Delta S = -7.0 (\pm 1.0) \text{ e.u.}$$

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DEPARTMENT OF APPLIED CHEMISTRY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGES OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY,
CALCUTTA-9.

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